

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE DOCTORS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8050802>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 12-June 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 15-June 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 17-June 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

higher education, thinking, pedagogical communication.

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the scientific and experimental substantiation of the effectiveness of technologies for the formation of clinical thinking of future doctors when teaching gynecology in medical universities.

In the world's leading universities and research centers, special importance is attached to the implementation of creative mechanisms for the development of students' logical thinking through pedagogical communication. A number of scientific studies are also being carried out to develop a reflexive system for the formation of attitudes towards the professional activities of future medical workers in the process of teaching specialty subjects to students of higher medical educational institutions. In our country, much attention is paid to the rapid development of the social sphere, strengthening the health of the population, and developing effective mechanisms for the training of future medical workers. The development of professional knowledge, skills and thinking of future specialists on the basis of modern technologies, the formation of their innovative thinking and potential is becoming increasingly important in the teaching of psychology. As a result of the implementation of state health care reform programs, a fundamentally new system of high-tech specialized medical care has been created.

Specialized medical centers of the republic, including surgery, cardiology, eye microsurgery, urology, obstetrics and gynecology, pediatrics, endocrinology, therapy and medical rehabilitation, dermatovenereology, phthisiology and pulmonology, equipped with modern equipment and staffed by highly qualified doctors. Highly qualified specialists working in these centers undergo appropriate psychological and pedagogical training while studying at medical universities. This requires clarification of the socio-pedagogical features of the development of logical thinking in future medical workers, the development of mechanisms for the development of thinking through competence. The purpose of the study is to scientifically and experimentally substantiate the effectiveness of technologies for the formation of logical thinking of future doctors in the process of teaching psychology in medical universities.

Modern information technologies are widely used in teaching psychology to students.

Slides, videos, various exercises specific to

the subject of science are shown to students with the help of computers, of course, this situation is carried out under the control of teachers. In the process of teaching psychology, students are encouraged to improve, strengthen, clearly understand complex processes and implement visual perception. We can see promising aspects of the timely and effective use of computer technology, the effective use of technical achievements, the perfect training of the younger generation, the timely and effective use of computer technology. At present, in order to increase the student's ability to think independently, the independent work of students in higher educational institutions is of particular importance. When performing independent work in psychology, students perform it in the following order, observing the requirements for performing independent work. To gain points, the student must: work on situational tasks created by the teacher, each student must be independent and individual, create various questions and tests on the topic, choose a topic and prepare a document and presentation on it and show it to their teammates, prepare various games to cover the topic, be able to demonstrate the examination of the patient with the help of dummies, draw a conclusion, collect and enter new information via the Internet, approach it with evidence and examples. Independent work prepared by the student is summarized and evaluated by the teacher. These types of lessons help students acquire deep and solid knowledge and help them remember the subject perfectly.

With the help of video clips, students try to perform the techniques they have seen and heard practically and theoretically on their own, with the help and under the supervision of a teacher, and they try to eliminate some mistakes and shortcomings by repeating them on the spot. This is done under the supervision of the teacher and the correction of the mistakes made. Students improve their practical skills by comparing them with the practices they see on the computer.

In teaching psychology and pedagogy to students, computer technology, which is considered one of the modern pedagogical technologies, takes its place with its own advantages. It helps students to see with their own eyes how difficult their chosen professions in the field of medicine are, using a computer to increase their interest in science, increase creativity, increase interest, make them feel more deeply responsible for their chosen profession. The convenience of multimedia lies in the fact that it can form specific knowledge and skills even for a student who has no training in the chosen topic, as well as restore forgotten knowledge. In addition, long-term storage and consolidation of information is confirmed. For future specialists, the method of placing such information indelibly in memory is invaluable and relevant. Therefore, in universities, the use of multimedia is widespread both in practical and lecture classes. In conclusion, we can say that the use of innovative technologies during the lesson will expand the possibilities of future specialists in a deeper understanding of the general theoretical sections of science, structural patterns, and replenish them. The importance of this lies in the fact that it develops logical thinking in students. The sooner he begins to correlate the knowledge of future specialists with situations that they will face in the future, the more useful. In the process of teaching pedagogy and psychology, the psychological and pedagogical features of the development of logical thinking in medical students as a factor in high-quality professional training, the integration of the dynamic aspect of the dynamic aspect of the doctor-client interaction are considered. relationship, a conscious attitude to making rational decisions in treatment, with medical pedagogy, through a student-

centered approach, determined by the provision.

In the process of learning, students create a closely interconnected closed chain of thinking and thinking.

The process of independent thinking consists of the following steps:

1. In the activity of independent thinking, first of all, the problem to be solved must be thoroughly understood by a person. If a question or problem is not put before a person, then he does not even think about anything. He doesn't even look at it. The person is prone to laziness. Consequently, the more accurate and complete information a person has about the issue that needs to be resolved, the easier it will be for him to find ways and means for its rational solution. All the knowledge that is most needed to solve a problem or question is to know and be able to apply important relationships, customs, and connections. For this, the process of memorizing situations and techniques encountered in personal experience is carried out, and their application in solving similar problems.

2. A hypothesis is put forward related to the question or problem, the stages are analyzed and opinions are expressed on the solution. Different methods are considered, they are compared and the most effective methods are highlighted. It is necessary to test the hypothesis using certain criteria. To test this, similar cases are compared in terms of morality, form, and structure. At the same time, the material of creative imagination is widely used, that is, the creation of creative plans, the creation of generalized images, the visualization of target results, the perception of indicative relations are carried out. To make sure it is true, the system of mental behavior is tested and refined with the aim of making some changes. The hypothesis is mentally analyzed and synthesized by logical methods, its important features are highlighted, quick judgments and conclusions are made regarding its correctness and validity.

3. If the hypothesis put forward for the theoretical solution of the problem is determined as true or false, then it is forced out of the object of thinking, and new hypotheses, thoughts, assumptions are accepted or invented. A new practical hypothesis is mentally tested several times, and then recommended for testing in order to put it into practice. Most of the above considerations are related to the solution of structural and technical issues, the creation of discoveries, inventive proposals, rationalization, and the introduction of technological devices.

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